

Management Information Systems in Architecture College Libraries of Hyderabad

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***Abstract** - The present study examine the Management Information Systems in Architecture College Libraries of Hyderabad. Automation of libraries has availed the libraries to keep pace with the latest Development. This has additionally facilitated precision, flexibility and reliability in the library and information centre. Management Information System of libraries reduces the perpetual work and preserves them and brings precision and speed. Functional and operational efficiency and effectiveness of an organization, worth its name depend upon the quality of decisions made. A Scientific and rational decision-making needs complete, timely and relevant information, signifies the role of management information system in organization. The majority responde 10(91%) have Study space and Resources adequacy and also 9(82%) have Budget allocation, Library facilities and Maintenance facilities and very few libraries are fully automated.*

Keywords: Management Information Systems, Architecture Colleges, User studies, Automatio, Decision making

Introduction

The application of management information, in particular that derived from automated systems, has a potentially important role in relation to current problems faced by libraries. Management information has been available to librarians for a long time, based on manually compiled records, but libraries have not always had access to computer generated information. Consequently, the potential of Management Information Systems has lain hidden. By the late 1980s, however, most academic libraries in the United Kingdom had computerised the main library operations. The first part of this paper considers the growing importance of a formal planning process in library management. Next it discusses the relationship of the library planning process and Management Information Systems, and describes how computer systems can be used as a tool to produce management information. It then goes on to review the development of automated library systems. "Information system consists of a set of people, procedures and resources that collect, transforms and disseminates information in an organisation."¹ When Information systems are designed to provide accurate, timely, and relevant information needed for effective decision making by manages, they are called Management Information System.

Architecture is defined as the art and science of designing buildings and structures. Doing architecture requires strong technical knowledge in the fields of engineering, logistics, geometry, building techniques, functional design and ergonomics. It also requires a certain sensibility to arts and aesthetics. Traditionally, architecture courses are always found at the crossing of those domains. The profession of architect demands a certain ability to synthesize

information coming from very different areas, and architects often assume the position of leader, mediator or centralizer in groups made of very different specialists. Architecture college libraries are playing vital role in Management Information Systems.

In addition to supporting decision making, coordination and control, Management Information System may also help managers and workers in analyzing problems, visualize complex subjects and create new ideas.”

Management Information System (MIS)

Management Information system is concept and combination of three words:

Management: It means to manage information in a organize manner to make information useful.

Information: Information refers to collected, organized and meaningful data.

System: A system means co-related components which works together for a same goal.

Definition of MIS

A formal method of collecting timely information in a presentable form in order to facilitate effective decision making and implementation, in order to carryout organisational operations for the purpose of achieving the organisational goals”. —Walter I. Kennevan

Management information system (MIS) is one of the major computer based information systems. Its purpose is to meet the general information need of all the managers in the firm or in some organizational subunit of the firm. It supports the planning, control and operation functions of an organization by furnishing uniform information in the proper time frame to assist the decision makers" (Waston, 1987). The information in MIS describes the firm or one of its major systems in terms of what has happened in the past, what is happening now and what is likely to happen in the future. The information is made is available in form of periodic reports, special reports and output of mathematical simulations. All managers use the information output as they make decisions to solve the firm’s problems (Raymond, 1990).

Review of Literature:

Nosrat Riahinia, Sara Behimehr and Sohrab Seify (2015). purpose of the study was examining the intermediary managers” attitudes of National Library of Iran toward management information system (MIS). To this end, qualitative approach and collective case study methods were utilized. The statistical population consisted of all intermediary managers of the library. The findings revealed various types of managerial information which the managers need as well as the methods of obtaining it. Moreover, the results shed light on the managers” attitudes toward MIS advantages, the challenges of lack of MIS and barriers to deployment MIS in the library.

Jayant Deshpande (2014) this paper presents how to create an information system for introducing a new information service in the libraries and the information centers. Automation of libraries has availed the libraries to keep pace with the latest development and

additionally facilitated precision, flexibility and reliability in the library and information centre. Management Information System of libraries reduces the perpetual work and preserves them and brings precision and speed.

Velmurugan, C. (2013)The paper attempts to report the findings of a study to evaluate MIS in the educational institutions. Due to growth and developments in information and communication technologies have been impacting upon Educational organizations. The conceptual elements of MIS identified on the basis of theory in management and library and information science. The study explores the application of MIS in academic libraries and other knowledge centre in India. This principles and methods have been utilizing management information systems to improve the competency and efficiency of administrative services. Even though of academic institutions comprehensible equipment with computers and local area networks, there are a large amount of problems and obstacles basically of organizational and methodical character which are necessary to solve for successful MIS introduction.

Objectives:

- To study the existing Management Information Systems at Architecture College Libraries
- To evaluate the service expectations of the Architecture College Libraries
- To assess the utility of the present MIS to the Architecture College Libraries

Methodology and Data Collection

The following methodology has been employed to make the users survey of Architecture College Libraries. Questionnaire method is adopted to collect the data from the Architecture Librarians. The structured questionnaire is framed covering personal data, and various levels of management information system. There are 12 architecture colleges in Hyderabad affiliated to Jawaharlal Nehru Architecture and Fine Arts University, against questionnaire all the 11 college librarians were responded.

List of colleges under the study

Table-1 List of colleges under the study

S.No	Name of the college	Status	College Code
1	Aurora's Design Academy	Private	ADA-1
2	Aurora's Design Institute	Private	ADA-2
3	C.S.I. Institute of Technology	Private	CSIIT
4	Deccan School of Planning And Architecture	Private	DSPA
5	Jawaharlal Nehru Architecture and Fine Arts University (JNA & FAU), Hyderabad.	Government	JNAFAU
6	JBR Architecture College, Hyderabad	Private	JBRAC
7	JNAFAU-School of Planning and Architecture	Private	JNAFAUSPA

8	School of Architecture & Planning Jawaharlal Nehru Institute of Advanced Studies	Government	SAPJNIAS
9	Sri Venkateswara College of Architecture	Private	SVCA
10	Vaishnavi School of Architecture And Planning	Private	VSAP
11	Siri Vani School of Planning & Architecture	Private	SVSPA

Table-1 shows the list of colleges for study, there 11 Architectural colleges, out of 11 colleges two Government Colleges, remaining private management colleges which is affiliated to Jawaharlal Nehru Architecture and Fine Arts University, further investigation college code mentioned in the table.

Data Analysis

Table-2 shows the gender-wise respondents from the 11 colleges there 10 (90.91%) are male respondents remaining 2(18.18%) are female respondents. In case of Library working houses there 7 (63.64%) colleges working from 9.00 am to 5.00 pm., remaining working from 8.00 am to 8.00 pm.

Table-2 Gender-wise and Library working hours of responded colleges

Gender	No. of Responses	%
Male	10	90.91
Female	2	18.18
Total	11	100
Working Hours	No. of Responses	%
8 am to 8 pm	4	36.36
9 am to 5 pm	7	63.64
Total	11	100

Fig.1 Gender-wise respondents

Fig.2 Working hours of Architecture College Libraries

Status of automation in Architecture College Libraries

Library Automation refers to the phenomenon of mechanization of traditional library activities, such as acquisition, serial control, cataloguing and circulation control etc. This is the most important to evaluate the MIS concepts. Table-3 shows the status of library automation 11 Architecture colleges, 5 are fully automated colleges (DSPA, JNAFAUSPA, SAPJNIAS, VSAP, and SVSPA) and 6 are partially automated colleges and 3 colleges are automation not at all implemented.

Table-3 Status of automation of libraries

S.No.	College	Automation in progress	Partially automated	Fully automated
1	ADA-1	Yes	No	No
2	ADA-2	Yes	No	No
3	CSIIT	Yes	Yes	No
4	DSPA	No	No	No
5	JNAFAU	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	JBRAC	No	No	No
7	JNAFAUSPA	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	SAPJNIAS	Yes	Yes	Yes
9	SVCA	No	No	No
10	VSAP	Yes	Yes	Yes
11	SVSPA	Yes	Yes	Yes

Decision making responsibilities

Table-4 indicates the decision making responsibilities in architectural colleges, only 4 colleges having 'Library Committee'; except two colleges, remaining 9 colleges having 'Head of the department'; all 11 college have 'Teachers' and one college do not have 'Librarian'

Table-4 Decision making responsibilities

S.No.	College	Person Responsible for selection			
		Library Committee	Head of the department	Teachers	Librarian
1	ADA-1	No	Yes	Yes	No
2	ADA-2	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	CSIIT	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	DSPA	No	No	Yes	Yes
5	JNAFAU	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	JBRAC	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	JNAFAUSPA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	SAPJNIAS	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
9	SVCA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
10	VSAP	No	No	Yes	Yes
11	SVSPA	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

Implementation of Library Services

Table-5 shows the library services at college level, almost all 11 colleges have ‘Bibliography Services’, ‘Reprographic service’, ‘Digital Library service’, ‘Reference service’, ‘Current awareness service’, and ‘Printing service’. Only two college do not have ‘Inter-Library Loan service’; 5 colleges having ‘OPAC’ search facility, remaining do not have search facility.

Table-5 Implementation of Library services in Architecture colleges

S.No.	Services	AD A-1	AD A-2	CSI IT	DS PA	JNAF AU	JBR AC	JNAFAU SPA	SAPJN IAS	SV CA	VS AP	SVS PA
1	Bibliography Service	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	Reprographic Service	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	Inter-Library Loan Service	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	OPAC Search	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
5	Digital Library Service	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	Reference service	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	Current Awareness Service	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
9	Media services	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
10	Printing Service	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Satisfaction level of Commitment

Table-6 shows the Satisfaction level of Commitment on ‘Budget allocation’ for 11 architecture colleges. 9 (82%) ‘Satisfied’ with their allocation, 1 (9%) ‘Somehow satisfied’ and 1 (9%) are ‘Not satisfied’. In case of ‘External Funds’ 7 (64%) are ‘Not Satisfied’, 2(18%) are ‘Satisfied’ and 1 (9%) are ‘Somehow satisfied’. ‘Study space’ for library 10 (91%) are ‘Satisfied’ and 1 (9%) are ‘Somehow satisfied’. In case of ‘Resources adequacy’ 10 (91%) are ‘Satisfied’ and 1 (9%)

are 'Somehow satisfied'; 'Library Facilities' 9 (82%) are 'Satisfied' and 2 (18%) are 'Somehow satisfied'; 9 (82%) and there no 'Not satisfied' respondents. In case of 'Infrastructure' 7 (64%) 'Satisfied' with their infrastructure facilities, 3(27%) 'Somehow satisfied' and 1 (9%) are 'Not satisfied'. And adequacy' 9 (82%)are 'Satisfied' and 2 (18%) are 'Somehow satisfied' with 'Maintenance' of operational services.

Table-6 Satisfaction level of Commitment

S.No	Commitment	Satisfied N=11	Somehow satisfied N=11	Not Satisfied N=11
1	Budget Allocation	9 (82%)	1 (9%)	1 (9%)
2	External Funds	2 (18%)	1 (9%)	7 (64%)
3	Study space	10 (91%)	1 (9%)	0
4	Resources adequacy	10 (91%)	1 (9%)	0
5	Library Facilities	9 (82%)	2 (18%)	0
8	Infrastructure	7 (64%)	3(27%)	1 (9%)
9	Maintenance	9 (82%)	2 (18%)	0

Conclusion:

The majority responde 10(91%) have Study space and Resources adequacy and also 9(82%) have Budget allocation, Library facilities and Maintenance facilities and very few libraries are fully automated. Management Information System of libraries reduces the perpetual work and preserves them and brings precision and speed. Functional and operational efficiency and effectiveness of an organization, worth its name depend upon the quality of decisions made. A Scientific and rational decision-making needs complete, timely and relevant information, signifies the role of management information system in organization.

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